

Eurocentrism Obstructing the Path of World Literature and ‘Global Campus Novel’: A Study in David Lodge’s Campus Novel, *Small World*.

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Dheeraj Kumar
Research Scholar
Department Of English
Central University Of
South Bihar
GayaBihar, India

Saroj Kumar
Assistant Professor
Department Of English
Central University Of
South Bihar
Gaya, Bihar, India

Abstract

Even after the World War II, when we see the end of British, German, and French empires and the like, the Europeans did not get rid of their ideology of white man supremacy. Their Eurocentric ideas kept on flourishing, and it is reflected in their neglect of the remarkable works produced by the East. Even in the era of the postmodern world, where globalization is at great pace and producing an egalitarian and cosmopolitan society is of great concern, we see that Eurocentrism is deeply rooted in the literary consciousness of the European writers. From this perspective we discuss David Lodge’s so-called ‘global campus novel’, *Small World*, and expose Lodge’s Eurocentric attitude. The paper concludes with the idea that in the last five years when the world superpowers have been in conflict with one another and disengaged from the world forums, a campus novel written truly from the global perspective could provide a platform for interacting the academics from all over the globe and thus integrating the world society which is falling apart.

Keywords

Eurocentrism, Campus novel, World Literature, Globalisation.

Introduction

Eurocentrism is originally a strategy of the Europeans to keep the Europe at the center of the Globe and project its significance to the whole humanity, while projecting the rest of the world as worthless out of their consideration. Eurocentrism got its muscle strength by the colonial powers who colonized the great civilizations of India, China and Africa; and the brain power it got through the narratives of the religious and academic institutions of the Europe. Immanuel Wallerstein opines that “Social Science has been Eurocentric throughout its institutional history, which means since the time that there have been departments teaching social science within university systems.

Furthermore, as an institutional structure, social science originated largely in Europe... we are referring primarily and jointly to Western Europe and North America” (21). He accepts that “Even today, despite the global spread of social science as an activity, the large majority of social scientists worldwide remain Europeans” (21).

It was not just social sciences but the whole human history which got distorted and thus manipulated by the Eurocentric approach of the European and North American scholars. We include North America in the joint venture of the Europe, because North Americans projected themselves as the ‘civilizational partner’ of the Europeans throughout the period of colonisation and even in the post-colonial period. Researchers in the past few decades are working rigorously to counter the Eurocentrism embedded in the so-called world history created by the West. John Henrik Clarke claims that “Civilization did not start in European countries and the rest of the world did not wait in darkness for the Europeans to bring the light . . . most of the history books in the last five hundred years have been written to glorify Europeans at the expense of other peoples...” and that “When the light of culture came for the first time to the people who would later call themselves Europeans, it came from Africa and Middle Eastern Asia...” (3-4) Linus A. Hoskins in his article, “Eurocentrism vs. Afrocentrism: A Geopolitical Linkage Analysis” greatly agrees with John Henrik Clarke’s claim (248). In Hoskins’ view “the stark reality is that Eurocentrism had to - and still continues to - falsify, mis- represent, and distort human/world history as His-Story, His- Eurocentric-Story in order to maintain European global dominance/hegemony. Eurocentrism indeed represents a racist, divisive, a historical, and dysfunctional view of world history” (247).

Objective of study

Though David Lodge has been criticized for lacking the supposed artistic qualities in his novel, *Small World*, which is full of immoral jokes, Mews appreciates Lodge for his success in propagating the idea of "global campus novel" while experimenting with the 'setting' of campus genre; and also seriously questioning "the purpose of literary studies and of the institution of academic criticism itself" (726). We know that Lodge's *Small World*, is celebrated as a 'global campus novel' from the perspective of the 'setting' of the novel, but the present paper challenges its status of being a 'global campus novel' in a different context, that how it has tackled the issue, "the purpose of literary studies and of the institution of academic criticism itself", from the global perspective. So, we have the following research questions:

whether Lodge has truly embedded the idea of 'global campus novel' in his work *Small World* so that it could be categorized as a genuine text of the World Literature?

Keeping in mind what the above research question demand the analysis of the text, *Small World*, is exploratory in nature, and so we have adopted the methods of close textual analysis and discourse analysis. Our main objectives are to find out the area of specialization of the academic characters, in the field of literary studies; the origin of the literary texts which have been indirectly referred to or directly quoted from; the origin of the social science theories which have been discussed; the origin of the literary schools and movements which are highlighted; and the origin of the other source materials which have been used to provide different sorts of knowledge other than literary.

Review of Literature

Eurocentric ideas in the field of World History and World Literature flourished mostly in the colonial period but it was systematically protected and preserved even in the post-colonial era, by the academic institutions of the West. Watt refers Chakrabarty who questions the condition of "asymmetrical ignorance" developed in the discipline of history, by which

"Third World" historians were compelled to know about Europe and Europe's dominant position in the grand narratives of history, while historians of Europe or European settler societies felt no need to reciprocate because "universal" Europe was the subject of all histories and historical theory. Histories of India and other places in the Third World were subaltern or inferior (217).

Martha Nussbaum in *Not for Profit* comments on the courses in the United States during the 1950s and 1960s. The norm was "simply not to learn anything about Asia or Africa, their history and cultures, and not to learn anything about the major religions of the world, other than Christianity and Judaism" (87). About the Nussbaum's confession where she was made not to see the world as it was rather fixing her eyes mostly on Europe, Watt opines that Nussbaum actually "implies that Europe or "the West" was the world, or at least the paradigm for the world to follow and thus all that one was required to know of the world" (Watt, 212). There are other instances where we see that the students and scholars of the West were forced indirectly not to study the World as a whole but the West only. Brian Doherty et. al. say that "*Things Fall Apart* is likely to be the first adult African literature typically read by an American student" (100). It suggests the idea that all the remarkable works of the African literature produced before Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* were neglected.

Humanities developed even in the non-Western countries like China but it failed to gain the objectivity it requires to become of global significance and acceptance. In Sara Guyer's view the 'International Council of Philosophy and the Human Sciences (CIPSH)' is "an NGO formed in the last century to serve as the conscience of UNESCO in the aftermath of European fascism.", but "the humanities are underfunded in the United States and Europe" therefore, "CIPSH today is a benefactor of the contemporary Chinese state ..., and it is as much a Chinese organization as it is European." And the truth is that the humanities in China has become a puppet in the hand of political system of the state and it functions as the "soft power" of the Chinese Government. Guyer refers Wang while saying that "Chinese university today is, despite its explicit commitments to the humanities, as it was at its outset, a project "with military, industrial, and political motivations...the product of 'national salvation and survival'" (63). This sift of the power-center of the humanities from trans-Atlantic region to China results into "rearranging the global academic order and establishing a new ecosystem for the humanities" (62).

Analysis

Analysis of Lodge's *Small World*

In *Small World* Lodge has brought together a great number of academic characters through the mechanism of International seminars and conferences happening in different countries. The characters meet and discuss about their specialisation in diverse field of literature and literary theories, they share their ideological visions and the knowledge about the culture they belong to, and they even criticize each other's paper published in journals. The characters moves from one conference to another with motives like gaining of an additional academic achievement, or

fulfilling sexual desires, or escaping the boredom of living in the same working place for long time. There are two main narrative arcs; the first is about the love pursuit of Persse who chases Angelica from one country to another, but unfortunately he misses every time as he is about to catch her. The second narrative arc is about the election for the post of the UNESCO Chair of Literary Criticism. There are a great many characters, Philip Swallow, Morris Zapp, Fulvia Morgana, Jacques Textel, Michel Tardieu, who desire to get the post earnestly.

We are going to discuss the ways and means Lodge has adopted to execute his Eurocentric agenda- to make the European literature and theories as the only literature fulfilling the characteristics of World literature and global agenda, and to show the European culture as the superior culture which should be copied by the Eastern hemisphere. We will also discuss that how Lodge has promoted only the European languages and discriminated against the rest of the world.

Promoting Eurocentrism through the select literary and social science theories:

The professor-characters whom Lodge has chosen, have expertise in the literary and social science theories which are European in origin. Michel Tardieu is a professor of Narratology at the Sorbonne; Morris Zapp an American professor has firm belief in Deconstruction; Fulvia Morgana is a Professor of Cultural Studies at the University of Padua; Arthur Kingfisher has "become a leading figure in the New Criticism in the forties and fifties" (299).

We find that all the topics regarding literary theories, discussed in the conferences or in classrooms, are European in sense of their origin. Philip asks Morris about the conferences he is going to attend that summer. Morris's reply is that "Zürich is Joyce. Amsterdam is Semiotics. Vienna is Narrative. (...) Jerusalem I do know is about the Future of Criticism, ... It's sponsored by a journal called Metacriticism". (275) Fulvia attends a conference in Chicago on "the crisis of sign". When Morris asks about the attendees of conference, Fulvia says- "Oh, everyone you would expect. The Yale hermeneutic gang. The Johns Hopkins reader-response people. The local Chicago Aristotelians, naturally" (323). We come to know that Rodney Wainright who works in Australia, teaches his students in English the "Theories of Literature from Coleridge to Barthes" (289).

The narrator of *Small World* claims that "theory is what unites all these and many other conferences" (430). Now the question is whether the non-European, for instance say Asian literary theories should not be discussed. Unfortunately, we do not see any non-European theory discussed in the novel. Theories based on postcolonial world, are completely missing; and there is no reference to the critical thinking of ancient India and China in the field of literature. The only non-European writer whose theory has been referred to, is "Viktor Shklovsky"(p. 287) but that too with strategic negation. Morris tells Philip that "Habit ruins everything in the end, doesn't it? Perhaps that's what we're all looking for – desire undiluted by habit." Further he says, "The Russian Formalists had a word for it" (p. 287). Philip responds "'I'm sure they did,... But it's no use telling me what it was, because I'm sure to forget it'" (287). Philip's indifference to the Russian Formalists, shows the Lodge's Eurocentric attitude evolved from the democratic Europe's negation to the communist Russian literature. There is another incident where communist ideology is mocked in favour of capitalism. Lodge has developed Fulvia Morgana (an Italian professor) as such a character who studies Marxism and Lenin's philosophy, who professes communist ideology and criticizes bourgeois aesthetics and literary style, but herself lives a lavish life which the highest paid American professor (Morris) too, cannot afford. What it shows that ideologies like communism which got strong foot hold in non-European countries like Russia, China, Cuba, Vietnam, and North Korea, is unacceptable to European intellectuals.

Promoting Eurocentrism through highlighting the History of English Literature

We find that the professor-characters have got expertise in different areas of the English literature which have European origin, and they discuss those subjects either in their research work, or in their classroom, or in the seminars and conferences, or in their usual conversations. Howard Ringbaum writes "articles on English pastoral poetry" (296); Fulvia Morgana's husband teaches "Italian Renaissance Literature at Rome" (331); Persse McGarrigle working in Ireland, has written his "MA thesis on Shakespeare's influence on T. S. Eliot" (222). Philip wants to take some books to read in his journey to Ankara (Turkey): but as being "unable to decide between two late *Trollope novels*, he packed both, along with some *poems by Seamus Heaney*, a new *biography of Keats* and a *translation of the Divine Comedy* which he had been carrying around with him on almost every trip for the last thirty years ..." (366, italics mine).

There are a number of European writers whose works are referred to for one reason or another. For example, Morris and Angelica discuss about the idea of romance. Angelica considers romance "as narrative striptease, ..." and claims that "there's even a good deal of actual striptease in the romances." She gives the example of "Aristo's heroines", "The faerie Queene", "Madeline ... in "St Agnes' Eve"", "Geraldine in "Christabel" (241). We can see that how strategically- through Angelica's reference to Aristo, Edmund Spenser, Coleridge and Keats-Lodge has tracked down the history of English literature from the Classical period to the Elizabethan period, and finally to the Romantic period.

Out of the crowd of European writers, T S Eliot, Hazlitt, Milton, Spenser and Shakespeare have been prominently referred to, and Lodge does so very strategically but readers perceive it as happening naturally. T S Eliot has been highlighted because the hero of the novel, Persse, has done his MA thesis on him. Persse is asked about his research work by other academics whom he meets in international conferences. Persse's view about T S Eliot have been counter questioned by Sybil Maiden. He is asked by a publisher to submit his thesis for publication and get a good sum of money; his research work has been used in unauthorised way by an academic whom Persse challenges and the conference becomes chaotic. The name T S Eliot is also highlighted because in the latter part of the novel there is a wonderful description of a carnival festival in Vienna. Persse is in search of Angelica and he reaches Vienna. In the streets he comes across a number of strangers who are imitating the characters of *The Waste Land* and directly quoting the lines from T S Eliot's *The Waste Land*.

Angelica is Persse's crush and so he tries to pursue her from one country to another but every time he is about to catch her, he misses. He gets by sheer chance the trace of her new destination but in the form of a puzzle which is actually the lines of *The Faerie Queene* by Edmund Spenser. Persse searches the book at airport book stall and ticket counter, reads the specific stanzas, gets the idea that where his beloved would be right now and begins his journey to a new country. In the whole incident it is not just Angelica-Persse love story but the Edmund Spenser's work, *Faerie Queene* which gets prominence.

There are remarkable episodes regarding Milton's Paradise Lost and Hazlitt's works. The name of other writers like, Sigmund Freud, Northrop Frye, Louis Althusser, Jacqueline Susann, Harold Robbins and Jack Higgins, also keep coming for some reasons.

Promoting Eurocentrism through the characters' journey in the physical territories of the English Literature

Like the History we are also attracted towards the Geography of English Literature. We are made to visit a number of geographical locations which are either the birth place or working place or burial ground of some renowned European writers. Yeats wrote a poem while living at the shore of "the Lake Isle of Innisfree" (446). There is an incident where Persse has to go with some students to visit the place where Yeats lived. When Philip organizes a conference in Rummidge (England) the conferees visit "George Eliot's childhood home" and "Anne Hathaway's cottage" (261). In Rummidge there is a place named "Ye Merrie Olde Round Table" where "mock medieval banquets" (262) are organized. The name of the place evokes the ideas related to the Aurthurian romance, as the name of the place,- Stratford-upon-Avon (311), evokes in the readers' mind the name of Shakespeare.

Promoting Eurocentrism through giving space only to the European journals

The name of the literary journal TLS (Times Literary Supplement) comes a number of times for different reasons and a narrative arch, indirectly gets developed around this journal. It happens that Philip's book is critically appreciated by Rudyard Parkinson and thus his name starts echoing in the academic circles as one of the suitable persons for the UNESCO Chair of Literary Criticism. Morris fails to digest this event; the popularity of Phillip, he is later frustrated by knowing that the same Parkinson has criticized his paper in the same journal. Thus, the name of TLS develops a narrative space for its unique identification that how the academics of different countries use it to appreciate or chastise one another on the basis of their personal relationship. One might say that Lodge has ironically criticized the European academics, but the overall result is that the names of only the European academics occupy the narrative space and atleast the name of a European journal gets highlighted. There are other Euro-American based journals which have been mentioned: Metacriticism, Sunday Times, Wall Street Journal, Reader's Digest, MLA, Time Magazine, The Listener, the New York Review of Books.

Promoting Eurocentrism through the celebration of the birth centenary of the European writers

We see that there are incidents where European professors go outside Europe to deliver lectures but somehow their lectures are based on some European writers. Philip visits Turkey for "lecturing on Hazlitt." (287) When his wife asks "Are they very interested in Hazlitt in Turkey?", Philip replies: "I shouldn't think so, but it's the bicentenary of his birth." (pp. 287-288). This means Europeans know that people outside Europe are not interested in the Hazlitt's works. Later we come to know that it is true. We are told that the news that Philip will lecture on Hazlitt, "has struck dismay into the English faculty at Ankara [Turkey], since the only member of the teaching staff who knows anything about the Romantic essayists (...) is absent on sabbatical leave in the United States; and nobody else in the Department, at the time of receiving the message, had knowingly read a single word of Hazlitt's writings." (306) Morris who was once a fan of Jane Austen confesses that in 1975 he "kept getting invitations to Jane Austen centenary conferences in the most improbable places – Poznan, Delhi, Lagos, Honolulu" (274). We might interpret that Morris's using of the phrase "the most improbable places" is in the sense that it was beyond his expectation that he would be invited to lecture on Jane Austen on the places like "Poznan, Delhi, Lagos, Honolulu".

The above two incidents one with Philip and another Morris, suggest that the academics outside Europe have already developed a normalcy in cherishing the European writers even though they have not read these writers at all. So, the students of these non-European countries- Turkey, Poznan, Delhi, Lagos, Honolulu- would get manipulated to celebrate the European writers and unknowingly develop a culture of European domination.

Promoting Eurocentrism through the translation of European literature into non-European languages, and their adaptation for stage performances

Lodge has made us know that European writers are not just known outside Europe they are celebrated greatly by the translation of their works and its adaptation for stage performances. When Persse visits a bar in Tokyo, he meets a few Japanese professors and common men who are well aware of the works of Shakespeare. Akira, a Japanese academic, confirms Persse that he translates only Ronald Frobisher, a British author, but his colleague Professor Motokazu Umeda is a "translator of Sir Philip Sidney" (488). Akira next says that Motokazu "will know more of the old Shakespeare titles.", and Professor Umeda comes up with "'The Mirror of Sincerity' (*Pericles*), 'The Oar Well-Accustomed to the Water' (*All's Well That Ends Well*) and 'The Flower in the Mirror and the Moon on the Water' (*The Comedy of Errors*)" (pp. 487-488).

We see that Persse appreciates those titles. In the bar there is a man "who translates maintenance manuals for Honda motorcycles, volunteers the information that he recently saw a play by Shakespeare performed by a Japanese company, entitled, 'The Strange Affair of the Flesh and the Bosom.'" Persse confesses that he does not "know that one". Akira explains him that the original title is "*The Merchant of Venice*" (pp. 486-487). There is, "Lust and Dream of the Transitory World," which Akira confirms is the version of "*Romeo and Juliet*". There is "Swords of Freedom" which Persse guesses as "*Julius Caesar*?" and Akira confirms that he is "correct." Persse takes the translated version of English dramas delightedly as saying: "there's the makings of a good parlour game here. You could make up your own ... like, 'The Mystery of the Missing Handkerchief' for *Othello*, or 'A Sad Case of Early Retirement' for *Lear*" (p. 487). Here again interestingly we do not see any text of the Eastern origin getting translated in the west and stage-performed through adaptation.

Promoting Eurocentrism through the election of the UNESCO Chair of Literary Criticism; a so-called world literary forum

Through authorial narration Lodge has tried hard to falsify the idea that he is considering the whole world. The narrator tells the readers: "Oh, the amazing variety of langue and parole, food and custom, in *the countries of the world!* But almost equally amazing is the way a shared academic interest will overcome these differences. *All over the world*, in hotels, university residences and conference centres, ... *people of every colour and nation* are gathered together" (429, italics mine). Contrary to what the narrator promises that the whole world has been considered, we see that the attendees and topics regarding literature or theories discussed in the conference of MLA come only from the European origin.

Persse joins the MLA conference on Morris's suggestion that he might get Angelica there. Persse is "slipping into the back of lectures on 'Time in Modern American Poetry' and 'Blake's Conquest of Self' and 'Golden Age Spanish Drama', putting his head round the door of seminars on 'The Romantic Rediscovery of the Daemon', 'Speech Act Theory' and 'Neoplatonic Iconography'" (511). Persse does not get Angelica there. In a state of disappointment when he returns "from a forum on 'The Question of Postmodernism'" he passes a door which has a handwritten notice as saying: "Ad Hoc Forum on Romance" (511). If we minutely observe the episode, we would come to realize that whatever the lectures Persse attends during his search

of Angelica, all these lectures are one or the other way based on some European writer, text or theory.

The narrator claims that in the MLA there happens "discussions on *every conceivable literary subject*" (504, italics mine) but the title of the subjects he mentions are showcasing only European literature:

"from 'Readability and Reliability in the Epistolary Novel of England, France and Germany' to 'Death, Resurrection and Redemption in the Works of Pirandello,' from 'Old English Riddles' to 'Faulkner Concordances,' from 'Rationalismus and Irrationalismus im 18. Jahrhundert' to 'Nueva Narrativa Hispanoamericana,' from 'Lesbian-Feminist Teaching and Learning' to 'Problems of Cultural Distortion in Translating Expletives in the work of Cortazar, Sender, Baudelaire and Flaubert.' (p. 504)."

It clarifies Lodge's intention that he has no wish to give the non-West its due credit.

Promoting Eurocentrism through code mixing and code switching

When a European language other than English is spoken by a character, and it is mentioned in its original typography not its English derivative, its visual appearance makes the linguistic identity of the character alive; and no matter the reader understands that language or not, its typographical distinction invokes in the reader's consciousness the national identity of the character in question. Interestingly, only European characters are allowed to use such linguistic variation. The novel is full of such instances where the characters use the Italian or French or German words, accordingly their native language, in their usual conversation which generally happens in English, but such code mixing and code switching do not happen in case of non-European characters. We have example of the Turkish people whom Philip meets in his visit of Ankara, but their Turkish words are not assimilated in the narration. Hassim is a driver at the British council in Turkey. The narrator says, "Hassim, who spoke no English, relieved him [Philip] of his suitcase and led the way to the Landrover" (p. 410). When Hassim does not speak English, he would definitely speak Turkish, but the Turkish words he uses get no place in the text and his linguistic identity is not acknowledged. In other incident Philip is waiting for Joy at the railway station. When the train starts, he saw Joy rushing through the crowd to catch the train. Philip wants to get off the train, but "The man with the whistle, protesting in Turkish, tried to push Philip back into the train" (p. 417). Here too, the Turkish word of the railway staff is missing in the narration. In another incident a party is organized after the arrival of Philip. He asks Akbil about his drink. When Akbil leaves to get the drink his wife, Oya, too goes along with him as announcing: "'Mrs Simpson also needs a refill.' She took Mrs Simpson's glass and almost pushed Akbil towards the door." The narrator gives us Akbil's reaction: "'Why did you not stay with them?' Akbil muttered to Oya in Turkish. 'They will think us rude.'" (pp. 413-414). We can see that the original Turkish words have not been quoted. Like this the original Japanese and Korean words are missing from the text when Persse visits Tokyo and Seoul. As a result, the indigenous aura of the Japanese, Turkish and Korean people, do not come in the limelight.

One may defend Lodge by arguing that Lodge has not mentioned a single word of Turkish because he himself might not know the Turkish language. Here our counter-argument would be that if Lodge does not know Turkish then how he has translated Turkish into English. For example, "Why did you not stay with them?' Akbil muttered to Oya in Turkish." So, it would not be wrong to say that of not using the Turkish words, is the Lodge's deliberate choice. Second thing regarding the technical aspect of narration, is that how we could consider the narrator as omniscient one as he claims if his narrator does not know Japanese, Turkish, Korean and other non-European languages? The humorous part is that contrary to excluding the linguistic identity of the non-European characters, the narrator is much interested in telling the readers that how one thing say, egg is spoken in different European languages.

Even the character, Robin Dempsey takes the same course as that of the narrator, while using European languages only, to elaborate the Saussure's linguistic theory. Robin Dempsey, Angelica and Persse discuss the idea of Structuralism. Robin elaborates the Saussure's theory of the "arbitrariness of the signifier" (234). Persse asks to give him examples so that he could follow. Robin says, "the same animal is signified by different acoustic images in different natural languages. For instance, "'dog" is chien in French, Hund in German, cane in Italian, and so on." He goes further to elaborate the idea: "And if we are to believe language rather than our ears, English dogs go "woof woof", French dogs go "wouah wouah", German dogs go "wau wau", and Italian ones "baau baau"" (234). Though it is a farfetched idea but it has serious implication; so, we raise this question that Robin could also use the Indian, Russian, Chinese or African version of the word- dog- in his illustration but he has not done so.

Promoting Eurocentrism through focusing on the dialect and accents of the characters

Lodge in many incidents has taken caution to maintain the characters' style in sense of their use of dialects, and supposing that the typography of the dialects would might confuse the reader so he provides the reader sufficient information through the narrator's comment on the characters' usage of dialect of a particular region. We have an excerpt below where Philip is talking to his son. It is noticeable to see how his son speaks:

Hurrying downstairs, he passes his son, Matthew, on his way up. *"Ullo, our Dad,"* says Matthew, whose current humour it is to pretend to be a working-class youth from the North of England. 'Shouldn't you be at school?' Philip coldly enquires. *'Trooble at t'pit,'* says Matthew. (p. 316, italics mine).

Persse wishes to have sex with Angelica so he visits a shop to buy contraceptive. Below we have the extract of his conversation with the shopkeeper. It is interesting to see the way the shopkeeper who is a lady speaks:

*'Yis?'*she said listlessly.

Persse felt throatled by his embarresment. He wanted to run ..., but his limbs refused to move.

'Kinoielpyew?' said the girl impatiently.

Persse stared at his boots. 'I'm after wanting some Durex, please,' he managed to mutter, in strangled accents.

'Small meedyum or large?' said the girl coolly. (pp. 258-259, italics mine)

Persse listens to Angelica father's story that how he got Angelica and her sister as newly born babies left in aeroplane. Angelica father's says, "I worked for KLM in those days, I was on duty the day the plane landed with those two little stowaways. They were parked in my office for a while, cute little things. Gertrude – my wife – and me, we had no children, not by choice, something to do with Gertrude's tubes' (*he pronounces the word in the American way as 'toobs'*)" (470, italics mine).

Above we can see that how much toil Lodge has made to make the reader notice that the character in question is using dialect. The same thing Lodge has done to make the reader notice that the given character is though speaking in English but tinged with his/her native accent.

Morris Zapp comes Rummidge to attend the conference. He meets Persse whom he asks: "Say, is this where the conference is being held?" the narrator's immediate remark is that Morris asked, "in an *American accent*". (p. 229, italics mine). Persse tries to convince his cousin Bernadette to leave the nightclub job and return her home which she dismisses: "'I cannot go home,' she said in a voice which, though hoarse from too many cigarettes and, no doubt, strong drinks, still retained the *lilting accent of County Sligo*" (333, italics mine). For another conferee the narrator says, "On the rostrum, a man with a pale face and a skullcap of blond hair was speaking into the microphone in *Germanically accented English, biting off the consonants and spitting them out as if they were pips*, gesturing occasionally with a black-gloved hand." (p. 397, italics mine) When the stewardess in the airplane addresses the passenger as saying, 'Ladies and gentlemen,' the narrator remarks that "she said, in a *Kerry accent*" (p. 406, italics mine). When Persse along with students is crossing the Lake Isle of Innisfree, the subject of W. B. Yeats's most frequently anthologized poem, one of the students recites the line of Yeats: "I will arise and go now, and go to Innisfree" the narrator's immediate comment is that "an overweight matron in tartan Bermuda shorts and dayglo pink tee-shirt recited aloud in the *accents of Brooklyn*" (p. 446, italics mine).

Thus, it becomes clear that the writer has paid great attention to focus on the diverse accents of the characters who come from different parts of Europe and speak English as their second language. It is an inclusive approach of the writer to consciously give some space to the European languages other than English, because these are not the language of narration and if they do not get some space they would be completely marginalized, but such inclusivity we do not see when the writer deals with the Eastern or non-European characters (Japanese, Turkish, Korean) who though speak English as their second language but without any reflection of their native accent. As a result, the indigeneity of these non-European characters gets unnoticed..

On the basis of the above textual analysis, we have the following findings:

Findings

Only Western languages, literature, theories, culture and religion have been highlighted. We can see that Western hemisphere is united not only in sense of race, but literature, theories and the subjects which have origin in Greco-Roman civilization and tradition.

The idea of the UNESCO Chair of Literary Criticism which Lodge has implemented in his novel, *Small World*, is very misleading in sense of creating a false narrative about writing a 'global campus novel'. After WW II Europe and America were the main driving forces behind the establishment of the world forums like UNESCO and IMF. Rest of the world remained in illusion that they would become prosperous by these international institutions, while in reality these institutions became instrumental to the Europeans and Americans to rule over the rest of the world in a very tactical way proclaiming a rule-based order which every country should follow. The catch in their proclamation was the rules made for ruling the world, were actually made by the Europeans and Americans only, and the rest of the world did not get their voices to decide the World order. In the similar fashion by projecting the idea of UNESCO Chair of Literary Criticism in his novel *Small World*, Lodge has tried wonderfully to play the same tactic which his predecessors have been playing with the Eastern hemisphere. He gives the impression that the MLA Conference wherein the UNESCO Chair of Literary Criticism would be decided, is actually the meeting place of the world's largest academic gathering where scholars, professors, writers, publishers, people seeking jobs in academia, and the heads of different academic institutions for taking interview come from all over the World. Contrary to what the novel claims, we do not see the representation of the Eastern hemisphere at all. And the particular session about the selection of the UNESCO Chair of Literary Criticism, is actually for the selection of the WESTERN Chair of Literary Criticism.

Lodge is a British writer and so he is not just trying to establish the idea of white man supremacy or Euro-American supremacy over the world, but also putting effort to establish the British supremacy among the European countries. Therefore, he gives validation to the English language "as the international language of literary theory". In his words: "Being a native speaker of English helps, of course, because English has become the international language of literary theory" (430).

Eurocentrism creates a disheartening impact not just on the non-Western readers, even the European readers are drastically affected by. The European readers having a blind faith in the writers like David Lodge, would confine their knowledge only to the trans-Atlantic region (the so-called Western hemisphere) and keep themselves untouched from the reality of the Eastern hemisphere, thus ultimately restricting themselves from becoming the true Global citizens.

We see that there are characters who are non-European by origin but they appreciate the West a lot. Rudyard Parkinson is one such character who settled in Europe though he is originally "a South African who came to Oxford at the age of twenty-one and perfected an impersonation of Englishness that is now indistinguishable from authentic specimens" (p. 305). Akbil Borak is another character who spent some years in Europe (Hull) while doing PhD and returned to his native country Turkey, but develops a nostalgic relationship with the place, Hull, and always compares the worst of Turkey with his Utopia in the West. Lodge include one major character named Akira from Japan but he leaves no impression of Japan on the readers' mind except that he translates a British author. Through these characters, Lodge propagates the idea that the movement of the world is towards the West, and thus he allures the readers to feel inclined to the Western Literature.

It is noticeable to see that the pace of the novel, small world is really great. Its effect on the readers is that it gives little time to dig beneath the delusive narrative vision— of bringing a great number of academic characters in different locations in the same time frame— and inquire of the Lodge's hidden narrative agenda- to proliferate the Western literature monopoly and cultural ideology. Hence, the common readers who lack the research aptitude would be going to miss the Lodge's real motif.

The idea of global campus novel is based on two fundamental things: Self pride and understanding of globalisation. It is quite true that until and unless the countries, especially those who suffered from colonisation, promote their knowledge and culture, people of the West would not feel any urgency to acknowledge that, and the discrimination with India, China, Latin America, Africa and Arab countries in the novel *Small World* is one such example.

If the people of Third World countries are not proud of their language, literature, culture and traditions and they go for writing a global campus novel, we suppose that they would do more harm than the Orientalists, because they would marginalize their own indigenous language, literature, culture considering it as not of global importance.

One who wishes to write a global campus novel, must understand the agenda of globalisation. Globalisation in general is considered as the “processes of intensified economic, political and cultural exchange.” (Lundsgaarde, 13), and the term, “cultural globalization”, specifically “emphasises how the growing ease of cross-border communication and mobility enables the diffusion of ideas and shared cultural reference points” (Lundsgaarde,10). So, a global campus novel must reflect the idea of cultural globalisation which is very difficult to bring in to practice in the recent time because of the instability in the global economy. Country like America is focusing more on its nationalistic agenda which reduces the strength of globalisation. In 2017, the national security and economic advisers, H. R. McMaster and Gary Cohn, wrote that “the world is not a ‘global community,’ but an arena where nations, nongovernmental actors and businesses engage and compete for advantage” (Dobbins, 7). In the recent years the US leaders have developed a new theory to disengage from the global treaties, and they are working on “America first” policy (Shakeel and Ahmad Ramay, 8). World forums like UN (United Nations) and, WTO (World Trade Organization) and IMF (International Monetary Fund) have been losing its strength and they may become irrelevant in future.

Globalisation is in a state of jeopardy also because of the recent conflict between Russia and Ukraine where Ukraine is supported by the West; the conflict between Israel and Palestine which is actually a war between Israel and the Arab countries; the conflict between America and Iran; the conflict between India and Pakistan and the civil war happening in different countries like Syria. In such condition where mobility of the academics at global level is becoming more and more difficult to happen in real life, through global campus novel we might make it happen at least in utopian world. It would give the world a hope that it is still a better place to live together, and send a strong message to those power mongers who want to disintegrate the global society to have control over the weaker nations.

Conclusion

Winding up, we would say that identifying the problems of Eurocentrism is just limited to recognizing the marginalisation of the Eastern countries, but the more rigorous task is to eliminating the problem of Eurocentrism, which requires willingness, courage and labour of the non-European scholarly writers to produce the literary texts that truly internalise the idea of global campus novel, uphold the flag of globalisation and preserve the intent of global good. The present paper concludes with the idea that the narrative of a country would get space at world platform or in global literature if the country has significant influence on the global economy, politics and peace; because the narrative- soft power goes with the hard power of the country. Therefore, the under developed and the developing countries of the Global South, need more power to get their voices in the World Narrative.

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